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The value of industrial design in relation to GDP globally

It measures the incidence of industrial designs registered in a country relative to the size of its economy, expressed in terms of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) adjusted for purchasing power parity. This indicator allows us to assess how much a country invests in and develops industrial designs relative to its overall economic capacity. In other words, it does not simply count the total number of industrial designs, but it weighs them according to the economic size of the country, offering a more comparable measure on an international level. This variable is particularly useful for understanding the intensity of innovation and industrial creativity of a country in relation to its economic wealth. A high value of this indicator suggests that the country has a high concentration of creative and industrial design activities relative to its economy, while a low value may indicate a lesser focus or capacity in this sector. It is an indicator used to analyze a country's competitiveness and innovative capacity in the global context, providing insights into industrial development and creativity policies. The analyzed data refer to the period between 2016 and 2022.

The value of industrial design in relation to GDP globally in 2022. At the top of the list, China, South Korea, and Turkey stand out with a value of 100, suggesting that these countries are leaders in the production of industrial designs relative to their economy. China, in particular, with its vast market and growing industrial capacity, has been able to integrate industrial design as a key element of its economic development. South Korea and Turkey, while having smaller economies compared to China, demonstrate high creative intensity, reflecting significant investments in innovation and intellectual property. Following are countries like Mongolia and Italy, with values of 94.1 and 86.5, respectively. Italy's presence among the top ranks is indicative of its historical and current role in design, particularly in the fashion, furniture, and automotive industries. Mongolia, on the other hand, represents a surprise, suggesting that despite its smaller economy, the country has made significant progress in the industrial design sector, possibly through targeted development strategies and the internationalization of its productions. Germany and France, with values of 72.9 and 70.6, respectively, are among the advanced economies that maintain solid performance in the industrial design field, supported by their strong manufacturing base and tradition in engineering and applied arts. The presence of Morocco with a value of 62.7 highlights the emergence of new creative centers in countries historically not considered key players in the industrial design field. Countries like Malta, the United Kingdom, and Spain, with values ranging from 61.1 to 51.8, also show good performance, reflecting diversified economies and the importance of industrial design in their productive sectors. The position of the United Kingdom is particularly interesting, given its history of innovation and design, especially in technology and consumer sectors. In the mid-range of the ranking, countries like Moldova, Jamaica, and Portugal, with values between 48.3 and 42.7, indicate that even smaller economies can have a significant impact on industrial design, albeit with limited resources. These countries likely leverage specific market niches and a strategy of specialization to compete internationally. As we move down the ranking, it is observed that more developed economies, such as Japan and the United States, have relatively low values, at 25.5 and 6.3, respectively. This could

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reflect market saturation or a different innovation strategy that does not focus strictly on industrial design. Japan, in particular, known for its technological excellence, might have a more integrated approach where design is just one component of a broader innovative ecosystem. Finally, at the lowest positions, we find countries like Brunei, Guatemala, and the Dominican Republic, with very low values, ranging from 0.2 to 0.1. These values indicate a marginal presence in the field of industrial design, probably due to less developed economies, limited infrastructure, or a lack of investment in the creative sector and intellectual property.

The value of industrial design in relation to GDP globally between 2016 and 2022. Starting with the countries that showed the greatest growth, Mauritius emerges as an extraordinary case, with a 790.9% increase in its industrial design index relative to GDP. This suggests that Mauritius has invested significantly in developing industrial design, perhaps through targeted government policies, innovation incentives, or increased manufacturing capacity. This growth could be indicative of an economy in transformation that is seeking to diversify beyond traditional sectors like tourism and agriculture. Another notable case is Yemen, which saw a 637.5% increase. Despite the socio-economic and political difficulties the country has faced in recent years, this figure may reflect resilience in the creative industries or an increase in design-related industrial activity in specific sectors. However, given the country's complex situation, this increase may be temporary or limited to a few industries. Zambia and Jordan recorded increases of 391.7% and 320%, respectively. These significant increases could indicate an expansion in industrial design capabilities, perhaps through investments in training, access to new technologies, or international partnerships that have allowed these countries to improve their competitiveness in this sector. Saudi Arabia, with a 233.3% increase, can be seen as an example of how resource-based economies are seeking to diversify by investing in creative and technological sectors. An interesting case is Jamaica, which saw a 191.9% increase. This result could be linked to greater global recognition of Jamaican design, especially in sectors such as fashion and crafts, which combine tradition and innovation. Cultural tourism may have played a role in this growth, attracting attention and investment towards local design products. Moving on to developed economies, France recorded a 58.3% increase, which is significant for a country with a long tradition in design. This increase could reflect continued innovation in the sector, supported by strong cultural policies, investments in education, and a solid industrial base. However, the growth in countries like France and the Netherlands (34.2%) is lower compared to some emerging economies, suggesting that while these mature economies continue to grow, they may not be able to compete with the rapid development observed in countries with expanding markets. On the other hand, the significant decline in countries like Moldova (-48.5%) and Ukraine (-50.3%) is likely attributable to the political and economic crises that have affected these nations. These countries have seen a deterioration in infrastructure and industrial capacity, reflected in a decline in industrial design production. Instability has likely reduced the attractiveness for investments and made it difficult to sustain creative and manufacturing industries. The case of Italy, which recorded a 13.5% decline, is concerning given its historic reputation in the design field. This decline could be linked to a series of factors, including increasing global competition, internal economic difficulties, and perhaps a delay in adapting to new digital technologies and design trends. It is important to note that Italy is not the only developed nation to see a decline; countries like Finland (-12.8%) and Sweden (-15.7%) have also experienced significant reductions. These declines could suggest saturation in the design markets or a relocation of design activities to countries with lower costs. Another significant example is Germany, which saw a 25.3% decrease. Germany, known for its engineering excellence and industrial design, might be facing increasing competition from emerging countries, despite continuing to be a global leader in technological innovation. The decline could also reflect a transitional phase where old industries are trying to reinvent themselves in an increasingly digitalized global context. The

extreme decline observed in countries like Guinea (-61.9%) and New Zealand (-71.3%) is alarming and could indicate a significant loss in innovation and industrial production capacity. This decline could be due to a range of factors, including brain drain, lack of investment in education and training, or inability to compete with global markets. The drastic reduction in countries like North Macedonia (-67.0%) and Ivory Coast (-73.7%) could be linked to internal structural problems, such as political instability, lack of adequate infrastructure, or excessive dependence on traditional economic sectors at the expense of innovation.

Economic policies. To promote an increase in industrial designs registered by origin, relative to GDP in billions of dollars at purchasing power parity (PPP\$), it is essential to implement a series of targeted economic policies that address the various challenges and opportunities in the sector. The first and most important of these policies is investment in education and specialized training. It is essential to create an educational ecosystem that not only trains designers and creatives with advanced technical skills but also integrates training in entrepreneurship, intellectual property management, and innovation capabilities. Academic institutions, universities, and specialized schools should offer courses and programs that combine theory and practice, encouraging collaboration between students and local industries. Another crucial dimension is support for start-ups and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the industrial design sector. SMEs often represent the beating heart of innovation but lack the necessary resources to adequately protect and enhance their designs. Economic policies that facilitate access to credit, offer tax incentives, and create dedicated investment funds can provide these businesses with the support they need to develop and register their designs. In this context, it is also crucial to simplify bureaucratic procedures for registering industrial designs, reducing costs and the time required to obtain legal protection. Intellectual property protection is another fundamental pillar. Ensuring that designers and companies can effectively protect their products from imitations or infringements is essential to encourage innovation. Governments should collaborate with international and regional organizations to strengthen intellectual property protection regimes, while also providing legal assistance and informational resources to companies seeking to register their designs internationally. Another aspect to consider is the promotion of industrial policies that encourage collaboration between different sectors. Industrial design is not an isolated sector but intersects with many other industries such as manufacturing, technology, and culture. Promoting partnerships between companies from different sectors can generate synergies that lead to innovative and more competitive products on an international level. For example, integrating digital technologies into the design process can open new frontiers in product innovation. In this context, it is useful to promote innovation hubs and industrial clusters, where design, manufacturing, and technology companies can closely collaborate. These hubs can be facilitated through public investments in infrastructure, incentives for business installation, and the creation of shared spaces where ideas can be freely exchanged. These clusters should also be connected to international networks to ensure that local businesses have access to the latest global trends and technologies, while also promoting the export of national design products. Digitalization is another key element. The transition to a digital economy represents both a challenge and an opportunity for the industrial design sector. It is necessary to adopt policies that support the digitalization of SMEs by offering incentives for adopting advanced design software, additive manufacturing (such as 3D printing), and other emerging technologies. Additionally, digital platforms can be developed to facilitate access to international markets, allowing companies to present and sell their designs to a global audience without traditional geographical limitations. Governments can also promote the internationalization of industrial designs through targeted trade policies. Free trade agreements and international economic partnerships should include specific chapters on the protection of industrial designs, ensuring that design products registered in one country are also protected in foreign markets. Domestically, policies that encourage

exports and participation of companies in international fairs and exhibitions can increase the visibility of local designs and create new market opportunities. It is particularly important for governments to support the participation of design firms in major global industry fairs by offering financial and logistical support to ensure that even small companies can present their innovations on international platforms. It is also crucial to encourage sustainability in industrial design. With increasing environmental awareness, consumers and industries are shifting towards more sustainable and environmentally friendly products. Governments can promote sustainable design through regulations that incentivize the use of recycled materials, the design of long-lasting and easily repairable products, and the reduction of the overall environmental impact of production processes. Additionally, funding for research and development of new sustainable technologies in design can help position a country as a global leader in industrial sustainability. The importance of culture and heritage in industrial design should not be underestimated. Many countries have a rich cultural heritage that can be an inexhaustible source of inspiration for design. Policies that encourage the valorization of local traditions and their integration into modern design can create unique and highly distinctive products in the global market. Furthermore, promoting local design through national and international marketing campaigns can strengthen a country's brand as a center of creative excellence, attracting tourists, investors, and talent. Support for research and development (R&D) is another essential element. Policies that incentivize R&D investments through tax credits or direct grants can stimulate innovation in industrial design. Collaborations between research institutions, universities, and industry can generate new ideas and technologies that give a competitive advantage to design products. Additionally, the creation of joint research laboratories and access to advanced infrastructures, such as rapid prototyping labs, can accelerate the development of new products. Finally, the importance of a stable and favorable political and economic environment for innovation cannot be overlooked. Industrial design companies operate best in an environment that guarantees economic stability, legal certainty, and a regulatory system that supports innovation. Governments must ensure that overall economic policies, including those on taxation, trade, and regulation, create a favorable environment for the growth of the industrial design sector. This also includes immigration policies that attract global talent, fostering the exchange of ideas and skills among designers from different cultures and backgrounds. In conclusion, to increase the number of industrial designs registered by origin and improve the ratio with GDP at purchasing power parity, governments must adopt an integrated approach that involves education, intellectual property protection, support for SMEs, internationalization, sustainability, and innovation. Only through a coordinated and holistic strategy will it be possible to strengthen a country's ability to compete globally in the industrial design sector, creating lasting economic and cultural value.

Conclusions. The value of industrial designs as a percentage of GDP decreased on average by -9.86% between 2016 and 2022. However, there are nations where the value of industrial design has grown significantly above the average, such as Mauritius with +790.90%, Yemen with +637.50%, Zambia with +391.66%, Jordan with +320.0%, and Saudi Arabia with +233.33%. There are also regions where the value of industrial designs has significantly decreased, such as Guatemala with -92.85%, Montenegro with -94.04%, and Bolivia, Panama, and Tajikistan with -100%.

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